

Ytterbium metal promoted reaction of diselenides with allyl bromide

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In the presence of chlorotrimethylsilane, ytterbium metal can promote the allylation of diselenides with allyl bromide to give the corresponding allylic selenides in good yields under mild and neutral conditions.

Allylic selenides are very important intermediates in organic synthesis. They take part in many rearrangements, for example, (3,3)sigmatropic rearrangement leads to heterocyclic compound containing selenium¹. Substitution reactions of allylic selenides with a variety of electrophiles² produce useful intermediates. Reductive homocoupling³, Diels-Alder reaction⁴, oxidation⁵ and other reactions⁶ of allylic selenides are also known to give important compounds. Many methods have been reported for the preparation of allylic selenides, for example, the reaction of sodium with selenophenol and allyl bromide⁷, the reaction of diselenides with sodium borohydride⁸. Our group have studied the reaction of allylsamarium bromide with diselenides^{9,10}.

Results and Discussion

The allylation of diselenides with allyl bromide promoted by Yb/TMSCl system is presented in Scheme 1. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Yb/TMSCl promoted reaction of diselenides with allyl bromide

Compd. no.	R	Time h	Temp. °C	Yield %
1	C ₆ H ₅	2.5	20-25	80
2	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	3.0	20-25	76
3*	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	3.0	20-25	79
4	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	3.0	20-25	77
5*	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	2.5	20-25	84
6*	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	2.5	20-25	81
7	<i>i</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	2.5	20-25	83
8	CH ₃ CH ₂	2.0	50	60
9	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₅	2.0	50	63
10	CH ₃ CH ₂ CH(CH ₃)	2.0	50	50

*New compound.

Scheme 1

In our experimental work, it was found that ytterbium metal neither reacts with allyl bromide to form allylytterbium bromide as does samarium nor promotes the allylation of diselenides with allyl bromide directly. However, in the presence of a catalytic amount of TMSCl, ytterbium promotes the allylation of diselenides with allyl bromide easily. On the other hand, it has been found that in the presence of TMSCl, ytterbium does not react with allyl bromide to form allylytterbium bromide. The phenomenon suggests that the reaction of diselenides with Yb activated by TMSCl initially affords Yb(SeR)₃ which reacts simultaneously with allyl bromide to produce allylselenides (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Although the mechanism of this reaction is not clear yet, a possible mechanism may be postulated as shown in Scheme 3. Ytterbium metal is activated by TMSCl to give the activated Yb*, which gives away an electron to diselenide to form [Yb⁺], and diselenide gets an electron to form a free radical (RSe*) and a (RSe) anion. The intermediate [Yb⁺] gives away another electron to the free radical and changes to [Yb²⁺], then the free radical gets the electron to form another anion (RSe). [Yb²⁺] gives the third electron to diselenides and becomes [Yb³⁺].

Scheme 3

It is quite clear from Schemes 2 and 3 that the free radical and anion of arylselenide are more stable than those of alkylselenide. The experimental results (Table 1) show that Yb/TMSCl system can promote the allylation of diaryl diselenides with allyl bromide smoothly to give the corresponding allylic selenides in high yields, but gives lower yields for dialkyl diselenides.

We found (Table 1) that the substituted groups on the aromatic rings may affect the reaction yields. If the substituted groups are electron-withdrawing, the yields are higher. We also find that the yields for substrates with electron-withdrawing groups in *ortho*-position or *para*-position are higher than those having substituents in *meta*-position, and with electron-donating groups the yield is higher in case of *meta*-substitution than in case of *ortho*- or *para*-position.

Experimental

^1H NMR spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded on a Bruker 80 MHz instrument using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard, IR spectra on a PE-683 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a HP 5989B spectrometer. Microanalysis was carried out on a Carlo-Erba 1160 instrument.

Tetrahydrofuran was freshly distilled from sodium/benzophenone ketyl before use. Metallic ytterbium and other chemicals were commercially available and used as such. The reaction was preformed in a Schlenk type glass apparatus under nitrogen atmosphere.

General procedure : Ytterbium powder (0.173 g, 1 mmol) and a catalytic amount of TMSCl (15%) were mixed at room temperature under a nitrogen atmosphere. The metal was then activated by warming slightly for about 15 min and being allowed to cool to room temperature. Diselenide (1.5 mmol) in anhydrous THF (18 ml) and freshly distilled allyl bromide (0.363 g, 3 mmol) were added to it and stirred at 20–50° for a given period of time (Table 1). The reaction was monitored by TLC. The reaction was quenched with HCl (0.1 mol dm^{-3} ; 5 ml) and extracted with ether (3 \times 30 ml). The crude product was isolated by usual manner and purified by preparative TLC using cyclohexane as eluent. All the products were identified : **1**^{7,9}, oil, ν_{max} 3080, 2940, 1640, 1480, 1180, 990, 910, 730, 680 cm^{-1} , δ 3.30 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, $=\text{CH}_2$), 5.0 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, SeCH_2), 5.50–5.95 (1H, m, $=\text{CH}$), 7.0–7.5 (5H, m, ArH); **2**¹⁰, oil, ν_{max} 3080, 2960, 1645, 1510, 1380, 990, 900, 830 cm^{-1} , δ 2.33 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.31 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, $=\text{CH}_2$), 4.85 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, SeCH_2), 5.60–6.00 (1H, m, $=\text{CH}$), 6.70–7.60 (4H, m, ArH); **3**, red oil (Found : C, 56.70; H, 5.70. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{Se}$ requires : C, 56.88; H, 5.73%) ν_{max} 3370, 3030, 2920, 2360, 1580, 1470, 1280, 1210, 1160, 1060, 980, 910, 820, 770, 670 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.40 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.35 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, $=\text{CH}_2$), 4.85 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, SeCH_2), 5.50–6.00 (1H, m, $=\text{CH}$), 6.90–7.20 (4H, m, ArH), m/z 212 (M^+ , 21), 211 (3), 171 (13), 91 (100), 77 (6), 41 (20); **4**^{7,9}, oil, ν_{max} 3100, 2970, 2880, 1640, 1510, 1380, 990, 840 cm^{-1} , δ 2.30 (1H, s, CH_3), 3.33 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, $=\text{CH}_2$), 4.75 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, SeCH_2), 5.50–5.90 (1H, m, $=\text{CH}$), 6.70–7.50 (4H, m, ArH); **5**, light yellow oil (Found : C, 46.56; H, 3.80. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{ClSe}$ requires : C, 46.68; H, 3.92%) ν_{max} 3050, 2930, 1635, 1580, 1456, 1435, 1250, 1200, 1130, 920, 750 cm^{-1} , δ 3.45 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, $=\text{CH}_2$), 5.0 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, SeCH_2), 5.60–6.00 (1H, m, $=\text{CH}$), 6.90–7.40 (4H, m, ArH), m/z 234 (M^{+2} , 24), 232 (M^+ , 55), 191 (24), 112 (6), 41 (100); **6**, red oil (Found : C, 46.58; H, 3.86. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{ClSe}$ requires : C, 46.68; H, 3.92%) ν_{max} 3100, 2950, 2400, 1590, 1470, 1100, 920, 780, 750, 680 cm^{-1} , δ 3.53 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, $=\text{CH}_2$), 5.0 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, SeCH_2), 5.91–5.98 (1H, m, $=\text{CH}$), 7.18–7.49 (4H, m, ArH), m/z 234 (M^{+2} , 15), 232 (M^+ , 33), 191 (19), 112 (8), 41 (100); **7**^{8,9}, oil, ν_{max} 3110, 2950, 1650, 1480, 1180, 1100, 1000, 820, 690 cm^{-1} , δ 3.37 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, $=\text{CH}_2$), 4.83 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, SeCH_2), 5.60–6.00 (1H, m, $=\text{CH}$), 6.95–7.60 (4H, m, ArH); **8**⁹, oil, ν_{max} 2970, 2940, 2860, 1650, 1210, 1160, 1000, 910 cm^{-1} , δ 1.25–1.48 (3H, t, J 6.0 Hz, CH_3), 3.15–3.50 (4H, m, CH_2SeCH_2), 4.77 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, SeCH_2), 5.50–5.90 (1H, m, $=\text{CH}$); **9**⁹, oil, ν_{max} 3000, 2900, 2880, 1640, 1380, 1140, 1000 cm^{-1} , δ 1.00–1.65 (8H, m), 2.80–3.40 (3H, m, CH_2SeCH_2), 4.81 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, SeCH_2), 5.50–6.00 (1H, m, $=\text{CH}$); **10**⁹, oil, ν_{max} 3000, 2900, 2870, 1640, 1190, 990, 890 cm^{-1} , δ 1.00–1.72 (11H, m, allyl-H), 2.90–3.50 (4H, m, CH_2SeCH_2), 4.85 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, SeCH_2), 5.50–5.95 (1H, m, $=\text{CH}$).

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References

1. S. Patai and Z. Rappoport, "The Chemistry of Organic Selenium and Tellurium Compounds", Wiley, Chichester, 1986, Vol. 1; 1987, Vol. 2.
2. A. Spaltenstein, P. A. Carpiro, F. Miyoko and P. B. Hopkins, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1987, 52, 3759.
3. Y. Masygama, K. Yamada and S. Shimizu, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*,

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- 1989, **62**, 2913.
4. M. Roger and B. Danil, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1978, **61**, 3096.
 5. H. J. Reich, K. E. Yelm and W. Susan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 2503.
 6. S. Halazy and A. Kriet, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1981, **22**, 2135.
 7. E. G. Kataev, L. M. Kataev and G. A. Chmutova, *Zh. Org. Khim.*, 1966, **2**, 2244; E. G. Kataev, G. A. Chmutova, E. G. Yakova and T. G. Plotnikova, *Zh. Org. Khim.*, 1969, **5**, 1514.
 8. T. Hori and K. B. Sharpless, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1979, **44**, 4280.
 9. M. X. Yu, Y. M. Zhang and W. Bao, *Synth. Commun.*, 1997, **27**, 609.
 10. M. X. Yu, Y. M. Zhang and W. Bao, *Chin. J. Chem.*, 1999, **1**, 4.